

Proposed Marketing Strategy for Sustainable Growth of Persib Official Store

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ABSTRACT: PT Persib Bandung Bermatabat is in charge of the football club Persib Bandung, which is one of Indonesia's teams. The Persib Official Store, located at Graha Persib, 3rd floor, Jalan Sulanjana No. 17 Bandung, is managed and sold by PT. Persib Bandung Bermatabat. The Persib Official Store sells merchandise divided into three product categories: Fashion, Jersey, and Accessories. The issue that arises in this business is that sales fluctuate from January to June 2022. As a result, the purpose of this study is to learn about Persib Official Store's business situation and to recommend the best marketing strategy for increasing sales and becoming more competitive in the football merchandise industry's development. The research method uses qualitative research methods. Qualitative methods are used to obtain primary data and make observations from in-depth interviews with Persib supporters. The data collection is then used to make internal and external analysis. Internal analysis is used to gather information about Persib Official Store's internal conditions using Marketing Mix 4P analysis, STP, and VRIO analysis, while external analysis uses Porter's five forces analysis, competitor analysis, and customer analysis to determine external factors from the football merchandise industry. Furthermore, after carrying out internal and external analysis, the researcher used SWOT analysis and found the company's weaknesses, namely the lack of optimal marketing and social media strategies. Furthermore, after conducting a SWOT analysis, the researcher used TOWS analysis and found a solution to present a new marketing strategy by having a team digital marketing and optimizing their social media to increase customer awareness and purchase intention.

KEYWORDS: Internal Analysis, Eksternal Analysis, Marketing Strategy, Persib Official Store, SWOT Analysis, TOWS Matrix.

1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is one of the most populous countries in the world and is a football enthusiast country in the world. The football market in Indonesia is very wide, one of the factors is the fanatical supporters. Football has become an industry in Indonesia. [1] Indonesia ranks second in the list, with 77% of the population saying they are interested in football, just behind Nigeria, which tops the list with 83%. With a population of 270 million, there are 207 million soccer fans in Indonesia. Based on these survey data, Indonesia is the country with the second highest number of football fans. Fans of all football clubs in Indonesia are inseparable from their favorite team's merchandise. Social media is now a means for fans to support their favorite football club. No wonder the number of followers on the official social media accounts of football clubs is one indicator of the number of their fans. [2] Persib is the largest football club in Indonesia with a number of Instagram followers of 5.4 million followers.

PT Persib Bandung is a company that manages the Bandung football team. In addition, they run a business that produces and sells merchandise officially. [3] Persib is one of the football teams that has the biggest fans or supporters in Indonesia. However, there are still supporters who still cannot buy Persib products officially [4]. The first factor is the product, currently the Persib Official Store does not have intellectual property rights, allowing many competitors to buy and sell the same product easily. The second factor is price, the price offered by the Persib Official Store is relatively high in the consumer market considering the premium quality of goods and the added value provided to fans, so that competitors offer more affordable prices to consumers compared to the Persib Official Store. The third factor is the location, they only have one offline shop on Jl. Sulanjana. PT Persib Bandung Dignified does not have much space to expand its parking area. As a result, Persib fans look for other stores to buy Persib merchandise and have an impact on potential consumer buyers at the Persib Official Store, causing a decrease in sales. Apart from that, they also have online shops, such as the official website and sell through e-commerce channels such as Shopee, Tokopedia, Blibli, Tiktok shops which customers can reach to buy their wares. Even though Persib Official Store has an official website, they still sell more merchandise through E-commerce channels than the official website itself. The fourth factor is promotion, Persib Official Store currently does not have digital marketing personnel, so social media is not optimal, which only uses Instagram feeds, Instagram features and there are still no plans to create content, create campaigns and do good advertising.

2. LITELATURE REVIEW

Analyzing the company's internal conditions needs to use the VRIO analysis framework, to look at the company's internal resources to see whether they provide the company with long-term benefits both tangible and intangible. [5] VRIO Analysis means Valuable, Rare, Imitable, and Organized, the company can be strengths based on competitive advantage resources. to complete the company's internal analysis, it is also necessary to understand the 4P Marketing Mix strategy, namely to determine Product, Price, Place, and promotion [6]. [7] understand Segmentation, targeting, and positioning (STP) is a well-established marketing strategy because it is one of the most commonly used marketing models, and marketing professionals value it because it enables efficient and efficient communication. Analyzing the company's external conditions needs to use [8] customer analysis, to find out the customer's point of view, especially in terms of understanding related industries. Furthermore, to complement the company's external conditions it is necessary to use [9] Porter's 5 force analysis, to help understand the potential advantages of the industry and how to position the company to achieve and maintain competitive advantage. [10] From an external point of view, companies also need to analyze which competitors are directly in the same industry and understand the strengths and weaknesses of each competitor. by identifying internal and external conditions, [11] SWOT analysis can be used to determine the company's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. After that, the TOWS Matrix generates a strategy based on the Company's Threats, Opportunities, Weaknesses, and Strengths.

3. METHODOLOGY

Qualitative methods are used in this study. To better understand the company's business processes, qualitative research methods gather research understanding. Primary data and secondary data are the two categories of data used in this study. Persib supporters' managers and employees are respondents who participate in in-depth interviews which provide core data for this study. Primary data was also collected through an online questionnaire survey of Persib supporters. Internal company reports such as publications, magazines, newspaper articles and other media sources are used to collect secondary data for this research. Strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of the company will be identified through a SWOT analysis of all data. Each internal and external framework analysis findings through SWOT Analysis will be collected. Furthermore, the marketing strategy will be decided using the TOWS Matrix.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

A. SWOT

1) Internal Analysis: **Strength** and **Weakness**

Strength of Persib Official Store

- Has a license to sell their merchandise products
- Has access to players for marketing
- Big social media followers
- Products of superior quality and value

Weakness of Persib Official Store

- No digital marketing team
- Their social media is not maximized
- Not have intellectual property rights
- The price offered by the official Persib store is relatively high on the market
- Persib official store only has one offline store
- lack of attractive design
- Parking is limited at PT Persib Bandung Bermatabat

Internal Analysis: **Opportunity** and **Threat**

Opportunity of Persib Official Store

- New competitors find it difficult to enter this market because they must obtain a license from PT Persib Bandung Bermatabat

- Low substitute products in this industry
- Many vendors provide their services
- The era of digitalization makes it easy to market Persib Official Store through social media
- Competitors have no website

Threat of Persib Official Store

- Persib Official Store items are easily imitated
- Competitors offer lower prices than the Persib Official Store

B. Marketing Strategy for Persib Official Store Based on TOWS Matrix

Results are obtained through the internal and external conditions of the Persib Official Store based on the TOWS Matrix, which show several strategies that need to be considered and implemented at the Persib Official Store. According to the Persib Official Store, the following strategies can be implemented to develop new marketing strategies that can later increase customer awareness and purchase intentions.

1. Create Social Media Content Plan

The first step to create a social media strategy, Persib official store needs to make a content plan for their social media. One of the best marketing strategies that Persib Official Store should implement is the massive growth of social media users. This strategy aims to increase social media engagement and revenue. Persib Official Store must schedule social media content for the first time in order to plan effective social media content. This means that they must plan the content that they will post on social media. It is critical to schedule this content in order to reach the right audience at the right time. For example, the best times to post on Instagram are determined by the target audience's specific days and habits. This content calendar will greatly assist your social media plan in becoming more structured while also increasing audience growth. Whether it's Instagram content, TikTok content, or other social media content.

2. Execute Social Media Campaigns

The second step is to develop a social media strategy. After developing social media content, Persib Official Store must launch a social media campaign. Social media campaigns are necessary for Persib Official Store's success in building Brand Awareness for customers and later directing them to be able to buy merchandise products at the Persib Official Store. The goal of social media campaigns is to increase brand awareness, website traffic, and Persib Official Store sales. The social media campaign strategy that can be run by the Persib Official Store is by having a Meet and Greet event for Persib players and legendary players, giving product giveaways, and inviting followers of Persib Official Store social media users to participate. The importance of running a social media campaign stems from the fact that Persib Official Store can reach more customers, find the right media to pique customers' interest, and develop an effective marketing strategy for marketing activities

3. Maximize Customer Testimonials on Their Website

The author's next step in proposing a marketing strategy is to increase customer merchandise purchase transactions through the website in order to maximize their income. Because customer testimonials are important, Persib Official Store should display them. With testimonials, new prospective customers who are considering purchasing Persib Official Store products will be more helpful and confident because someone has already tried to buy them. They can display a collection of customer purchase testimonials on the landing page of their website, because customer testimonials are real proof that a product or service is of high quality.

4. Add a Live Chat Feature on Their Website

The next step in increasing transactions through the Persib Official Store website is to add a live chat feature, because live chat allows customers to interact in real time. When customers want to buy a product, they frequently ask questions about the product, such as price, stock availability, materials, and so on. With the live chat feature, potential customers can easily ask questions about the products offered by the Persib Official Store via their website.

5. Provides a Variety of Payment Methods on Their Website

To increase transactions through the Website, Persib Official Store must offer a variety of payment options to customers. Providing simple and flexible payment options such as accepting bank transfers from various types of banks if customers want to make online payments, going through minimarkets if customers want to make offline payments, and Persib Official Store can also follow trends such as payment in stages (Payletter).

6. Collaborate With The Community

Furthermore, the author suggests that PT Persib Bandung Bermatabat collaborate with club communities such as vikings, bomber and so on. Collaboration with the community, such as having special designs in the Persib Official Store fashion and accessories category, can increase sales volume; additionally, PT Persib Bandung Bermatabat can establish good relationships with their club community. The goal of collaborating with the club community is to gain a competitive advantage in the market while also expanding consumer reach.

7. Collaborate with Persib Players

Persib is one of the most popular Indonesian football clubs on social media. Football is inextricably linked to the players on the field. Apart from their influence in football, players also have a strong influence in the sale of football club merchandise. PT Persib Bandung Bermatabat has access to players who can promote club merchandise on social media. In order to attract customers and especially Persib club fans, Persib Official Store must maximize their sales by collaborating with club players. Persib Official Store can maximize revenue and raise brand awareness by collaborating with players.

8. Build a Second Offline Store

Finally, the author proposes to make PT Persib Bandung Bermatabat a long-term asset. Persib currently only has one offline store in the Jl. Sulanjana area, but they only have limited parking space access if customers want to visit. To avoid potential customers who want to come and buy directly from their offline store, PT Persib Bandung Bermatabat should build a second offline store in a strategic location with easy access to parking lots. because having a second offline store allows them to maximize revenue from the merchandise they offer customers.

9. Make Bundle Packages and Discount Promotions

In addition, the author suggested to PT Persib Bandung Bermatabat a strategy for creating bundle packages and discount promotions. The merchandise sold by Persib Official Store is relatively expensive in the market. To attract customers' attention, PT Persib Bandung Bermatabat should create bundle packages such as providing fashion, jersey, and accessories categories in a single package. They must also carry out discount promotions on a consistent basis, such as when there are old date promotions, when Persib wins matches, and so on. The advantages of creating bundle packages and discount promotions include increased sales volume, reduced warehouse stock, stable income, and the ability to compete in the market.

10. Have Digital Marketing Team

PT Persib Bandung Bermatabat doesn't have a digital marketing team right now, so their social media isn't as good as it could be. Digital marketing is a type of marketing that uses electronic devices connected to the internet and a variety of marketing strategies and digital media to talk to potential customers online and reach a larger market. A digital marketing team at PT Persib Bandung Bermatabat can help them sell more products, improve their brand's reputation, and get the most out of social media.

11. Have Intellectual Property Rights

PT Persib Bandung Bermatabat currently only has an official license to sell their merchandise products. They should have industrial property rights because it is so easy to manufacture and sell the same product nowadays. Because the benefit of intellectual property rights is to protect intellectual works from misuse or falsification by third parties, both at home and abroad. If PT Persib Bandung Bermatabat has Intellectual Property Rights, it will also have a positive image.

5. CONCLUSION

The company that manages and sells Persib merchandise is PT.Persib Bandung Bermatabat, which also houses the Persib football club. PT Persib Bandung Bermatabat was founded on August 20, 2009, following the separation of Persib Bandung from APBD,

with an address of Graha Persib 3rd Floor Jalan Sulanjana No. 17 in Bandung. As a result of fluctuating income in 2022, the intent to purchase from Persib Official Store will be disrupted. This phenomenon is caused by the fact that there are still numerous rivals or Persib club communities that sell unofficial goods, also known as KW goods, which are widely dispersed in physical stores and marketplaces bearing the Persib logo. As a result, the Persib Official Store's marketing is ineffective; product prices at the Persib Official Store are still relatively high for market consumers; and buyers who want to come directly to the Persib Official Store have limited access. More and more brands from similar businesses are appearing on the market, each with a unique design. Persib Official Store must raise brand awareness in order to increase customer purchase intentions. To increase brand awareness and customer purchase intentions, Persib Official Store requires marketing communications. According to the analysis, the Persib Official Store marketing communication program was still limited to Product, Price, Place, and Promotion. In terms of products, Persib Official Store currently lacks intellectual property rights, allowing many competitors to easily imitate and sell their products. Aside from that, the design of Persib Official Store fashion products and accessories is less appealing than that of competitors. In terms of pricing, Persib Official Store offers relatively high prices in the market, so competitors capitalize on this opportunity by imitating and selling at lower prices; additionally, Persib Official Store lacks a strategy for implementing good prices, such as package bundles and so on. Persib Official Store only has one offline store, which is located on JL. Sulanjana and has limited parking space. As a result, it influences potential consumer buyers who want to visit their physical store. They have an official website for online stores, and selling via e-commerce channels such as Shopee, Tokopedia, Blibli, and Tiktok shops where customers can buy their wares. Despite having an official website, the Persib Official Store sells more merchandise through E-commerce channels than the official website itself. Persib Official Store receives several deductions from its income for each sales transaction, which, of course, disrupts Persib Official Store's income. In terms of promotion, Persib Official Store currently lacks digital marketing personnel, so social media is underutilized, with only Instagram feeds and Instagram features used, and no plans to create content, create campaigns, or do good advertising. To solve the main problems based on Persib Official Store SWOT analysis, the researcher proposes a strategy of using TOWS Matiks to solve business problems and provide recommendations so that companies can increase customer awareness and purchase intentions. A suggested strategy for Persib Official Store is as follows:

1. Create Social Media Content Plan
2. Execute Social Media Campaigns
3. Maximize Customer Testimonials on Their Website
4. Add a Live Chat Feature on Their Website
5. Provides a Variety of Payment Methods on Their Website
6. Collaborate With The Community
7. Collaborate with Persib Players
8. Build a Second Offline Store
9. Make Bundle Packages and Discount Promotions
10. Have Digital Marketing Team
11. Have Intellectual Property Rights

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